

Historical Resolution of the Mathematical Structure of Modern Trigonometry at 1:3 Pythagoras (360/19) (Revision of Isaac Newton's Fallacy of Trigonometry.)

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ABSTRACT:

This paper is geared towards the students and admirers of Sir Isaac Newton, to assert by this paper, almost after 400 years; to remind him and them; that it is mathematically imprecise to calculate a curve or area of a circle, without the parity of numbers equations with correct trigonometry and equations of numbers, aligned to the great theorem of Pythagoras, specially Pythagoras 1:3, which is the keel of the universe of mathematics at subtended angle 360/19 degrees. The inverse curvature of the universe of mathematics (Universe itself) is precisely related to Pythagoras 1:1; 1:3 ; 1:5 as shown in this paper using the correct value of 360/19 degrees at Pythagoras 1:3; is easily mathematically plotted and as herein published, and Newton's attempt to describe curvatures by linear numbers equation is at best approximate.

The horizons and the curvature of the universe are precise based on non-linear equations, not approximate as per the rumination of Newton, as in the proof in the previous published paper (Divestiture of mathematics), 360/19 is the correct value in degrees at 1:3 Pythagoras which should have been suspected by the great master of mathematics Newton. The world of mathematics must come to terms with numbers and trigonometric diversions of Pythagoras. The intent is not to challenge the methods of Sir Isaac Newton, but to assert that on what mathematics he based his apparent logical approximations, that basis of mathematics is flawed; given that degrees as defined in the mathematics are precisely concordant with numbers($(360/2)/3=60$ precise), representing the constant factor 6.

The author maintains in this paper and the previously published paper the following, and provides ample mathematical proof of the keel value of Pythagoras 1:3.

1.1 Pythagoras= $360/8=45$ (90/2) degrees subtended

1:2 Pythagoras= $360/16=22.5$ (90/4) degrees subtended

1:3 Pythagoras= $360/19= 18.94736842105$ (90/4.75) degrees, subtended

1.4 Pythagoras= $360/24=15$ degrees (90/6), subtended

1:5 Pythagoras= $360/30= 12$ (90/7.5) degrees, subtended (90/7.5)

1:6 Pythagoras= $360/38$ degrees subtended

For Pythagoras 1:1;1:3;1:5, the arithmetic is simple and further proven under methods, as from above a factor of 90 degrees $(4.75-2) = (7.5-4.75)$.

The fundamental precise mathematical parity of the above Pythagorean precision is defined by the mathematical premise not understood by the approximation of Isaac Newton’s understanding of mathematics that degrees and numbers as understood currently .The revision is as follows

$$\left[\frac{\frac{A}{B}}{\frac{A}{C}} = \frac{(A - B)}{(A - C)} \right] (3.75)k: @1: 3 \text{ Pythagoras}$$

(22.5 degrees is the subtended angle at Pythagoras **1:2 :**)

It is a precise mathematical parity of numbers, that

$$\frac{1 + 2 + 3}{3 + 4 + 5} = 0.5, \text{ reflecting the basic parity of } 1: 3 \text{ as Constant}$$

By a simple arithmetic factor of 360 degrees the subtended Pythagoras 1:1; 1:3; 1:5(360/8; 360/19; 360/30): see resolution below in the methods section (3.75). Degrees must be concordant with numbers without exception.

$$19-8=11$$

$$30-19=11$$

$$\frac{30 * 19}{19 * 8} = 3.75$$

KEY WORDS: Divestiture of Current Mathematics, Isaac Newton’s approximations; Curvature of the universe (mathematical); fallacy of Isaac Newton’s mathematics of curvatures.

METHOD:

The method is based on Pythagoras triangulations, based on the correct subtended angulation. It is a surprise that Isaac Newton instead of assimilating the exact work of the great Pythagoras, chose to approximate mathematics, even in the binomial theorem. The author is here in this paper concerned with his clear understanding as presented herein rather than Isaac Newton’s mathematical fallacy; based on the correct numbers and the precise mathematics of Pythagoras’s understanding of “correct trigonometry” and the innate curvature of mathematics that Newton ill understood by the linear equation

$(n)^{\frac{1}{2}}. (n)^{\frac{1}{3}} \dots$ clearly do not have a linear relationship there should be a period.

The numbers must first be integrated by the trigonometry to obtain precision, and as is shown Newton’s work results mostly in approximations and numbers are basically curved in their innate expression, and as such all current trigonometry, plus the binomial theorem are approximate resolution of numbers . Only and exclusively at the angle 1:3 Pythagoras, (360/19 degrees) is bound space exactly ½ as proven in the reference. 1:6 is exact at (360/19)/2 degrees)

The trigonometric understanding of Sir Isaac Newton is at best approximate, still after 400 years and this paper seeks to bring on a mathematical standard to make trigonometry precise ,and to correct

$$(360/19) \cdot 45 = 26.05263157895$$

$$26.05263157895 / 6.94736942105 = 3.75 (k)$$

CONCLUSION:

Precision in all of mathematics is not by complex linear equation of numbers as established by that master of approximation Newton (did Isaac Newton describe or could he describe a perfect innate mathematical curve in terms of spatial measure) That was the fallacy of Newton that he never discovered or understood the precise singular role of the subtended angle at 1:3 Pythagoras, 360/19 degrees (even to this day its value is incorrect). Since the angle 360 /19 degrees has been shown to be precisely and exclusively perfectly divisible in the referenced previous paper, a circle can be rationally divisible at minimum 19 divisions and maximum at 38 rational. The relationship of the correct precise trigonometry compliment all numbers theorem when it comes to the curvature of space and mathematics divisions 19 +38 divisions representing Pythagoras 1:3 and 1:6 , at subtended angles 360/19 (1:3) and 360/38 degrees(1:6). Current Newtonian mathematical legacy is approximate, so is whole of Mathematics, because of poor understanding of the Pythagorean mathematics.

REFERENCES:

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The mathematical universe at 1:3; Mathematics and computer science journal, volume 10, December 2015.